

DEVELOPMENT OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN RELIGION

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Annotation: *This article describes the volitional qualities of a person, the role of religious factors in these qualities of a person, the stages of the development of volitional qualities. In addition, the difference in the development of volitional qualities in different types of personality is also shown separately.*

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A person considers a certain deed to be good, and by performing it a lot, a person's behavior in accordance with that deed is formed and strengthened. Accordingly, peopleIt is divided into four categories:

1. *Careless people.* They do not know the difference between right and wrong, beautiful and ugly. They are free from all beliefs. Being too dependent on pleasures, they cannot fully satisfy any of their desires. (That is, he leaves one taste and rushes to a better one, and then an even better one is found... As a result, he cannot fully fulfill any of his desires. This type of person accepts the treatment very quickly. Only he has a teacher, a He needs a murshid. He needs a desire to wake up in his heart and motivate him. Then he will soon become a person of good character.

2. *Ignorant and lost people.* People of this category know what is bad, but they are not used to good deeds, and their bad deeds seem beautiful to them. Although they have turned away from righteousness by being slaves to the desires of the world, they are aware of their shortcomings. Since the upbringing of this category is more difficult, several tasks are assigned to them. First of all, they should get rid of many vices that

have been firmly established in their hearts as a result of habituation to corruption. Then they should instill in their hearts the quality that motivates them to do good. So, if you roll up your sleeves and make a serious effort, this category of education is a wide field for mathematics.

3. *Ignorant, misguided and wicked people.* A person of this category believes that bad morals are good morals. In his eyes, this morality is right and the most beautiful. This vision in him will improve more and more. Therefore, the treatment of a person in this category is difficult, there is almost no hope for his recovery, and in rare cases he can find a cure for his pain. All these aspects increase the possibility of going astray.

4. *Ignorant, misguided, wicked and evil people.* A person belonging to this category is not only perfect in perversity, but he considers it a virtue to multiply vices, he is proud of it and thinks that these things increase his worth. The situation of this category of people is difficult. It is said about them: “To bring up an old man is hard work, and to bring up a wolf is to torment him.”¹

There are also those who believe: “As long as a person is alive, lust, anger, love for the world, and other behaviors will not cease from him!” This is a mistake. After all, those who hold this view understand that the purpose of moral education is to uproot and completely destroy the above-mentioned feelings.

Lust is a natural necessity. Its creation is intended for certain benefits. If the appetite for food is completely extinguished, a person will be doomed. If the sexual desire is cut, the offspring is cut. If the feeling of anger is completely destroyed, a person cannot fight against things that cause destruction. As a result, they kill a person. As long as there is lust in human nature, love for material things will not disappear. This love, in turn, leads a person to more lust, and even encourages him to accumulate wealth. The goal is not to completely eliminate these feelings, but to moderate them.

Temperance in anger is maintained in a beautiful form by being passionate and enthusiastic. Passion in its beautiful form is free from anger, anger, and all forms of

¹ Abu Hamid Al Ghasali. *The Revival Of Religious Sciences*. 2011.

cowardice. In a word, a person who has a moderate level of anger is internally strong and at the same time subordinate to the mind.

Through this information, it is revealed that a person can not only defeat the ego, but also educate it, subjugate it to the mind and thereby form a healthy will in the example of 4 types of individuals. It has been described that it is easy or difficult to educate a person's will depends on his behavior, character, and to a certain extent on his beliefs.

On the other hand, globalization, in which the forces against it are constantly growing along with development, and social networks are constantly influencing the behavior of individuals together with strong knowledge among young people who build the future of our country. It is also important to have a strong will. Based on the thoughts of the 1st President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov on will, we will not be mistaken if we say that as the spirituality of a person increases, his will also becomes stronger. Will is actually a firm belief.

A strong-willed person believes in himself and is not afraid to take on any difficult task. That is why you can rely on a strong-willed person. Such people can't look at you indifferently if you have any worries or problems. Without hesitation, he will stand by your side, try to help you as much as possible, overcome difficulties together with you. The presence of a person's will is the goals and tasks that are important for him. related to its existence. The more important and attractive these goals are for a person, the stronger his will, the stronger the desire, the stronger the achievement of them, all things being equal. An important goal for a person is an area that depends on his needs and interests. The emergence of will is related to the self-awareness of a person, his formation as a subject, and at the same time it determines the behavior of a person. The very existence of the concept of free will means that a person does not have unlimited freedom, because it depends on a number of external and internal conditions, but it means the freedom to choose how to react to these conditions and to oneself. From this point of view, it can be said that "will" is synonymous with the concept of "aspiration". In the religion of Islam (Sufism), they

cite “repentance” as a concept that strengthens a person’s will and determines its strength and duration.

The word repentance has 2 different meanings from the Arabic language:

1. Regret.
2. Self-correction, castigation.

Repentance, on the one hand, is a person’s emotional appeal to God for his sins, and on the other hand, it is also understood that he makes a willful effort not to repeat this situation in his future activities.

In the process of repentance, a person goes through 3 stages:

1. Cognitive - realizing mistakes. Its content in religion, its function of organizing human life, understanding of possible and impossible actions, learning about this information from Islamic sources (Qur’an and Hadith).

2. Emotional - remorse. Experiencing emotional distress or short-term stress as a result of imagining the consequences of an action that is contrary to orders.

3. Voluntary - striving hard not to return to sin, struggle with lust and Satan. During this process, the experience of a person in the cognitive and emotional stages plays an important role. As a result of these processes, it is understood that they reorganize their activities, develop or choose the means of the path leading to the goal even more perfectly.

It is in this process that love, especially love for God, has a strong positive effect on a person in order to ensure the quality, duration and continuity of his activity. To which of these stages one can reach, or how well one performs each stage, ensures a person’s spiritual growth. It also clarifies to what level a person can reach in the status and conditions of Sufism. The process of personal repentance is the science of understanding the great harm caused by sins and blocking between the servant and his beloved things. A person who is fully aware of this great harm will win his heart over vices. This process of realization is a complex mental state, and pain arises in the heart that has lost a loved one. As the feeling of loss in the heart increases, so does the intensity of pain. The heart regrets that he lost his beloved because of one bad deed. This pain in the heart is called remorse. After the pain completely takes over the inside, a special state called kasd appears in the heart (kasd is the intention to leave the sin, taking steps towards this goal). The word “repentance” has meanings such as turning

back, regretting, turning away from sins and turning to the Truth, and resolving not to repeat the sin in the future. According to Imam Ghazali, repentance is an immutable divine sunnah that emerges from the union of three things that require each other in turn: knowledge, state, and action. Each of these stages is a necessity for the next stage. Repentance has aspects related to today, future, and past: today you leave the sins that prevent you from your beloved; you are determined not to return to the sin of depriving your beloved in the future; this determination inspires hope that the mistakes of the past will be corrected. That is, it has certain conditions, which are as follows:

Scholars say: “Repentance has three conditions: to stop sinning, to be sorry, and to resolve not to return to it.” Some scholars say: “It is enough to be sorry for the sin committed in repentance. After all, this repentance requires a break from the sin and a commitment not to do it again. These two arise from remorse, that’s why they said: “Repentance is confession”. It is important to have knowledge about it and its consequences while the person cognitively understands its negative consequences.

In short, the level of belief affects the growth of the willpower of a person along with his cognitive side. In this case, a person needs a lot of willpower to distinguish between right and wrong actions in his activity and to consistently make this choice. A person can get it through love and sincere supplication to Allah. Through this, it is possible to ensure the unity and harmony of people in the society, and of course, they will engage in only good activities and conscientiously approach their work. It helps to be effective and successful in every profession.

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